

HOLOCENE CROSSROADS

— Managing the Risks of Cultural Evolution —

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Key concepts: causality, consciousness, creativity, cultural speciations, egalitarian/trans-egalitarian societies, engrams/exograms, geometrical patterns, Holocene, hunters-gatherers, iconic representations, Neanderthals, self-domestication, Upper Paleolithic.

